
COUNCIL ON
LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
THIRTY-FIRST
ANNUAL REPORT/1987

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ANNUAL REPORT/1987

1785 Massachusetts Ave., N.W.
Washington, D.C. 20036

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine* . . . Paris, 1588. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, with the following explanation: "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." The engraving has appeared in each annual report since that time.

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1. Resigned as Director; elected Director Emeritus, June 1987.

2. Resigned as Director; elected Director Emeritus, November 1986.

3. Mr. Liebaers succeeded Mr. Brooks at the November 1986 Directors' meeting.

4. Ending June 1987.

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5. Beginning February 1987.

6. Resigned, October 1986.

7. Resigned, May 1987.

8. Beginning November 1986.

PROGRAM REVIEW

Introduction

Not long ago we learned of an expression of concern that “CLR doesn’t stick to anything over a long period of time.” Looking back at our history, the assertion is valid. Although underlying aspirations have been remarkably constant for thirty-one years, specific programs do come and go.

There are natural cycles that characterize our activities. Some grant programs, notably those keyed to the needs of individuals, are on a regularly recurring schedule, but this is as much for the convenience of applicants as it is for ours. The Management Intern Program (13 years), the Faculty/Librarian Cooperative Research program (5 years), and other ventures such as the UCLA Senior Fellows, the ARL Institutes on Research Libraries for Library Educators, and Recent Graduates seminars are all examples of cyclical programs.

Of more interest are the life cycles of many of the most substantial CLR undertakings. The Bibliographic Service Development Program, brittle books, the Library Service Enhancement Program, and the College Library Program (in cooperation with the National Endowment for the Humanities) are a few examples that illustrate the volatility of our efforts—that is, if a cycle of five or seven years is evidence of volatility.

And, reviewing the history of CLR, a five- to seven-year cycle seems typical of many of the activities we initiate. It takes that long to verify a perceived need, to shape a program, to enlist assistance and participants, and to accomplish goals. In some cases, there are tangible products such as LSP protocols; in others, the goal is to institutionalize an activity (e.g., upgraded bibliographic instruction) or to put in place a needed new agency (e.g., to increase microfilming capacity). Sometimes the effort fails (the National Periodicals Center comes to mind), in which case the life cycle is considerably abbreviated.

In short, our charge is to help libraries, individually and collectively, to establish new and useful ways to do their work; it is not to do the work itself. Continuing attention to fundamental issues is something we can and do give. But CLR cannot support ongoing operations, however successful and important. A good test of the worth of any major new undertaking is the prospect of self-sufficiency.

As evidence that CLR, itself, cannot escape these cycles, we periodically initiate (or submit to) reviews of our own work. In 1973, the Ford Foundation (at that time the source of CLR funds) sponsored such a review. In 1982, a CLR Board special committee considered how our program might address the effects on libraries of the expansion and influence of commercial information services.

We are now looking ahead once again, and will seek help from many in the library and academic world during the fall and winter. By late spring, 1988, we plan to complete and make widely available a statement that will try to look over the horizon at academic and research libraries as they might be in the future. One thing is certain from the start: we need to look at CLR, not in isolation, but in an essentially new setting that includes numerous organizations and activities, many of which did not exist when the Council was established in 1956. Planning for CLR, and probably for most other academic enterprises, now begins by finding one's place rather than by assuming that there is one.

Most introductions to annual reports close with a formulaic request for readers' observations and suggestions, but this year, especially, we would welcome your thoughts about CLR and its future.

Warren J. Haas

The Year 1986/1987

The Council's grant activity is a mix of strategic planning and capitalizing on opportunity. The charts of grant activity over the past ten-year and three-year periods reflect the changes in program emphasis. Bibliographic services, by far the largest program element during the planning and development phase of the Linked Systems Project, are moving toward a more stable implementation phase and require less CLR support. Preservation, on the other hand, is experiencing a new popularity as the Commission on Preservation and Access proceeds with its agenda.

The newly defined research program is becoming established as UCLA's long-range planning project enters its second year and three other universities begin research initiatives, all of which take different approaches to learning more about the ways information is put to use in the university environment, identifying the changing requirements, and planning the university's response to the changes.

A small staff and limited resources also influence CLR activities. Consequently, some of the program areas have been maintained at a relatively modest level in 1986/87. A review of CLR programs scheduled for 1988 will determine areas for future emphasis.

CLR Program Trends: Summary of Grants, Contracts, and Projects

<u>Program Area</u>	<u>Percentage of total program expenses</u>	
	<u>10 years 1978-87</u>	<u>3 years 1985-87</u>
1. Bibliographic services	47%	19%
2. International activities	4	1
3. Preservation	7	23
4. Professional education	24	26
5. Management	4	1
6. Research	6	21
7. Library collections/resources/access	6	8
8. Miscellaneous	2	1
	100%	100%
Approximate totals:	\$11.2 million	\$3.1 million

Research

In late 1985, the Council on Library Resources expanded its program to encourage exploration—through analysis, research, experiment, and discussion—of many important topics pertinent to providing and managing the information resources needed for teaching and scholarship. The growing availability of information technology prompted the expanded effort, which is focused on the influence of that technology and the opportunities it presents for universities, their research libraries, and the process of scholarly communication in general. In particular, the program is intended to generate more information about (1) the future requirements of academic disciplines for library resources and services, (2) policy issues affecting access to information, and (3) the organization and management of all library and information functions in universities.

The general outline of the research program was shaped by the CLR Board after extended discussions with leading university officers, scholars, and librarians. Senior CLR professional staff members manage the program, which is divided into two parts: (1) university-based research activities to concentrate attention on the characteristics and use of information as well as the organization and management of information systems and services within universities; and (2) a research program that will encourage work by individuals with pertinent skills and interests. In both cases, the grants are meant to support work concerning the content and form of information, especially in the context of research and teaching, and to point the way toward giving coherence to future information systems and services offered by libraries.

Institutional Grants

The first institutional grant was awarded to the University of California, Los Angeles, to develop a long-range strategic planning process for libraries and information resources in the research university. This work is viewed as a prototype for efforts in other settings. Robert Hayes, Dean of the Graduate School of Library and Information Science, is the program director, and through his considerable efforts, most divisions of UCLA are directly involved and a university planning structure is in place. A number of exploratory studies have been funded, and they have, in turn, stimulated several substantial projects, including:

1. A reassessment of information resources for instruction in design, School of Architecture;

2. Planning for integrated information services, Graduate School of Management;
3. Development of an information system as an integral component of a new Hazardous Substance Research Center;
4. A supporting study for a multicampus project to produce a definitive edition of publications and manuscripts related to the voyages of Columbus; and
5. A study of information resources and accessibility to them for a new developing countries research program.

Most importantly, funds for analytical studies have in turn triggered important planning efforts in an increasing number of schools and divisions of the university.

To give recognition to the UCLA program and to encourage other universities to consider institutional research programs, CLR funded a meeting at Malibu, California, on September 7–9, 1986. Library and academic representatives from ten universities were invited to learn of the UCLA approach and to discuss the process of strategic planning. Two of the participating institutions, the University of Minnesota and the University of Illinois at Chicago, each subsequently developed proposals for university-based research activities, which were approved by the CLR Board at its June 1987 meeting.

The University of Minnesota will develop a model for information services to be provided through the library of the Hubert H. Humphrey Institute of Public Affairs. The project, managed jointly by staff from the Management Sciences, the Institute of Public Affairs, and the University Libraries, will be carried out in two phases. The first phase consists of five interrelated research projects carried out by interdisciplinary teams: information requirements assessment; information technology, resources, and services forecast; organization structure assessment; funding and recovery of costs; and policy and legal issues. The second phase of the project will be the actual design of the model system.

The University of Illinois at Chicago (UIC) will involve its Institute for the Humanities as the test site for a research program, with two objectives:

1. To engage scholars on campus in important questions pertaining to how they do their research, with what tools and techniques they do their research, and how the research is disseminated; and
2. To develop, collaboratively, the long-range policies that will influence the way the library can assist further in the process of scholarship.

Two UIC librarians will join the Institute during 1987/88 to prepare papers on scholar-library issues and to identify the policy considerations that emerge from their discussions with fellow participants. A conference at the year's end

will concentrate on a topic pertinent to CLR's interests and judged to be important by Institute fellows.

A third new university-based research activity is a more specialized project, and one of great potential importance. CLR has funded Carnegie Mellon University to plan a year-long research seminar to explore the structure of texts in machine-readable form. The seminar participants will include representatives of publishing companies and library networks, as well as Carnegie Mellon computer science faculty members and library and information systems planners. Upon the successful completion of the planning phase, CLR will fund a portion of the costs for the seminar itself during 1987/88.

CLR professional staff have been actively involved in the development of the university-based research activities and will continue to maintain close liaison with them as they unfold.

Individual Grants

As a way of assembling in one source what is known about research and communication in the humanities and social sciences, CLR commissioned Anita Lowry and Junko Stuveras, reference librarians at Columbia University, to compile a bibliography, divided into three major sections: Computers and Society; Characteristics of Scholarly Research and Communication; and New Technologies in Scholarly Research and Communication.

The first individual research grant was awarded to Elizabeth Liddy and Robert Oddy, professors at Syracuse University, for a study of "Textual Analysis of Information Need Statements and Document Abstracts." Combining methods drawn from linguistics and from computer science, the investigators will use techniques of discourse linguistics to explore techniques for effectively identifying those few documents in a large bibliographic database that offer the most helpful response to an individual's need for information.

Research Program Projects, 1986/1987

Carnegie Mellon University

To establish a study group to examine the purpose and uses of electronic text in education and research, and to discuss production and distribution of electronic text.

Columbia University Libraries

To assemble a selected, annotated bibliography on the influence of the information revolution on scholarship in the humanities and social sciences.

European Foundation for Library Cooperation

To stimulate cooperative research and development in European librarianship.

Abigail Dahl-Hansen Studdiford

To identify public policy issues that affect major United States research libraries and the effect of these issues on federal funding for research libraries.

Syracuse University

To study the structure of problem statements and abstracts as a basis for improving information retrieval system design.

University of Illinois at Chicago

To engage fellows and scholars at the Institute for the Humanities at UIC in examining topics related to strategic planning issues for the research university.

University of Minnesota

To develop a model academic information center as part of the Humphrey Institute of Public Affairs Library.

University of California, Los Angeles

To develop a university-based research program focused on the issues, problems, and needs for research with respect to long-range strategic planning for libraries and information resources in the research university of the future.

Program Meetings, 1986/1987

Strategic Planning for Information Resources in the Research University
September 8–9, 1986 (Malibu, California)

Access to Information

The research library community, resolute in its objective to make information more widely accessible to all who need it, continues to seek collaborative and practical methods for sharing resources. A comprehensive bibliographic system is the first step toward access to the information itself; much has been accomplished, but the actual delivery of documents is the next activity that requires concentrated effort.

Cooperative research grants (listed on page 24 of this publication) have often addressed topics pertaining to equitable access to information. Examples of topics studied jointly by librarians and teaching faculty include the information requirements of different categories of users; the quality of online databases and their influence on the process of research; the questions raised by providing information in alternate (non-book) forms; and the complexities of consortial governance.

Several organizations were funded to consider questions related to providing access to information in new ways or to new categories of users.

A grant was made to the American Antiquarian Society for the final phase of the North American Imprints Program. The grant will enable the American Antiquarian Society to complete the machine-readable cataloging of the remaining pre-1801 publications and to adjust and enhance the records so they can be successfully integrated into the Eighteenth-Century Short Title Catalogue.

The American Historical Association was awarded a planning grant for a new *Guide to Historical Literature*. A panel of advisors will address the question of the need for new reference guides to be in machine-readable form so that information can be distributed in a variety of ways.

The needs of users of the public library were considered in a centennial symposium, "From Asphalt to Crabgrass," at the Enoch Pratt Free Library (Baltimore, Maryland). Changing demographics and economics were examined in terms of the new requirements being placed on urban public libraries.

The Research Libraries Group (RLG) was funded to develop a paper on the use of the RLG Conspectus as a collection management tool; Anthony Ferguson of Columbia University, in consultation with others familiar with the Conspectus, produced the paper. RLG is also creating a national database of

information about public records using the Archives and Manuscripts Control (AMC) format.

The International Council for Scientific and Technical Information published the results of its comparative study of the use of serials by the principal interlibrary loan organizations in France, the United Kingdom, and the United States.

Access Projects, 1986/1987

American Antiquarian Society

To assist in completing a machine-readable catalog of materials printed before 1801 in the United States and Canada, and to integrate the records with those in the Eighteenth-Century Short Title Catalogue.

American Geographical Society

To plan for a new *Columbia Gazetteer of the World*.

American Historical Association

To conduct a planning meeting for a new *Guide to Historical Literature*.

Trudi Bellardo, Catholic University of America

To complete a history of the development of online information retrieval systems.

Enoch Pratt Free Library

To provide partial funding for the Enoch Pratt Free Library Centennial Symposium on metropolitan libraries facing the future.

International Council for Scientific and Technical Information

To compare the use of serials by major interlibrary loan organizations in the United States, France, and the United Kingdom.

The Library of Congress

To help fund a symposium on incunabula in American libraries.

The Pennsylvania State University

To enable Charles Townley to prepare a manuscript for library practitioners on developing library consortial relationships.

The Research Libraries Group, Inc.

For partial costs of travel for Library of Congress personnel attending the RLG Archives, Manuscripts and Special Collections Task Force meetings.

The Research Libraries Group, Inc.

To coordinate a project to create a national database of descriptions of state government records within the Research Libraries Information Network.

The Research Libraries Group, Inc.

To analyze the RLG Conspectus as a collection management tool.

Virginia Foundation for the Humanities and Public Policy

To conduct a series of seminars on southern writers for librarians.

University of Kentucky

To enable Lois M. Chan to compile a bibliographic guide to indexing languages used in online bibliographic databases.

University of Michigan

To examine attitudes of faculty in selected disciplines concerning shelving books in storage facilities and to test the influence of enhanced access and delivery services on those attitudes.

University of Pittsburgh

To enable Anne Woodsworth to investigate the role and organizational relationships of information managers in universities.

Program Meetings, 1986/1987**Access to Information for Public Library Users**

September 19, 1986 (Boston, Massachusetts)

Improving Subject Access to Information

May 14, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

Bibliographic Services

Supplementary funding for the Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP) has ended, but CLR maintains a strong interest in bibliographic matters, and key committees responsible for Linked Systems Project (LSP) applications continue to receive assistance from CLR.

The LSP Policy Committee met three times during the year to consider priorities for applications of the link and to begin consideration of the economic implications of linking. LSP priorities, established by the participants in December 1986, include: (1) completing work on authorities implementation; (2) developing the capability to transfer bibliographic records between participants; (3) assuring that local system linkings to the four participants will be identical and LSP-based; (4) developing the capability to provide intersystem searching for shared cataloging; and (5) developing the capability to handle messages and interlibrary loans.

To help accomplish the work that is implicit in the priorities agreement, the Policy Committee decided to expedite work on the Bibliographic Analysis project by concentrating initially on the specifications for categories of bibliographic records that will be the target of the new coordinated cataloging program.

The Technical Committee (established to assist the Policy Committee) was concerned principally with the question of migration from LSP protocols to the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) standards. In the absence of accepted standards, the Linked Systems Project was developed along the lines of Standard Network Interconnection (SNI) protocols. With the present trend toward the open system interconnection reference model, technical representatives from the participating networks are committed to making the necessary modifications to conform to the new standards. The Technical Committee has produced a strategy and timetable for migration to ISO standards that has been accepted by the Policy Committee. Members of the two committees are listed in Appendix A.

In November 1986, the CLR Board approved the request of the Library of Congress (LC) and eight research libraries for funds to establish a coordinated cataloging program, as a natural complement to the growing emphasis on collaboration among libraries in building and preserving research collections.

The intent of the program is to increase the number of bibliographic records produced and to improve the timeliness of the availability of such records by enlisting the assistance of a limited number of libraries that (a) maintain extensive acquisitions programs in some or many subject areas and (b) have staff specialists with exceptional bibliographic skills.

The coordinated cataloging program anticipates full implementation of the Linked Systems Project, expected to be operational in 1989. Libraries participating in direct cataloging contributions to LC are: University of California, Berkeley; University of Chicago; Harvard University; University of Illinois; Indiana University; University of Michigan; University of Texas at Austin; and Yale University. In the next year, a research team will be formed to undertake the analytical work required to assess results and develop further the cooperative production of standardized records.

CLR contributed to work under way at Northwestern University to implement the Standard Network Interconnection in NOTIS, an important and much-used library system. The hardware and software to be developed can be used by the many other IBM-based NOTIS installations in academic and research libraries.

Elaine Svenonius, of UCLA's Graduate School of Library and Information Science, organized and conducted a conference on the Conceptual Foundations of Descriptive Cataloging. The conference, held in California on February 14-15, 1987, was based on a series of commissioned papers by experts from libraries and library schools. A publication from the conference will be issued in the coming year.

Karen Markey (University of Michigan) and Diane Vizine-Goetz (OCLC, Inc.) have received a grant to test and evaluate automated techniques to link subject terms entered by users of online catalogs with the controlled vocabulary of the online catalog. Library of Congress Subject Headings have only recently been made available in machine-readable form, and library systems designers will be faced with the problem of incorporating machine-readable subject headings into the existing bibliographic files.

At the request of the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, CLR's grant to develop an interface between the Triangle Research Libraries Network and OCLC for the exchange of bibliographic records using SNI was rescinded. OCLC experienced delays in its Oxford Project (OCLC's new online system) and decided that work on the North Carolina project could not proceed until the new OCLC system was operational.

Bibliographic Services Projects, 1986/1987

Columbia University

For a study to measure the impact of online public access catalog implementation on all aspects of public services at the Columbia University Libraries.

Linked Systems Project

Participants: The Library of Congress, the OCLC Online Computer Library Center, The Research Libraries Group, and the Western Library Network.

To design, develop, test, and implement a standardized telecommunication link, or Standard Network Interconnection, to permit exchange of data, initially between the LC, OCLC, RLG, and WLN computer systems and, ultimately, between any two computer systems.

To implement the exchange of authority records, using the Standard Network Interconnection.

To analyze requirements and develop additional functional specifications for the online exchange of bibliographic records and related information, using communication links developed in the Linked Systems Project.

National Information Standards Organization

To support service as secretariat for International Standards Organization Technical Committee 46 (Documentation), Subcommittee 4 (Automation in Documentation).

Northwestern University

To develop a combination of hardware and software that will enable NOTIS, and other systems operating in a similar environment, to communicate with other library systems using the standard protocols.

OCLC Online Computer Library Center

For partial support of work to develop OCLC's Linked Systems Project communications interface and software for the authorities application.

OCLC Online Computer Library Center and The University of Michigan

To test and evaluate automated techniques to link subject terms entered by online catalog users with the library catalog's own controlled vocabulary.

Stanford University

To investigate end-user searching of bibliographic databases by comparing the effectiveness and costs of using the DIALOG command language with the Institute for Scientific Information's Sci-Mate intermediary software.

University of California, Berkeley

To cover programming costs for a database of full text transcriptions and bibliographic records of Italian lyric poetry and associated music, 1450–1650.

University of California, Los Angeles

To conduct a workshop on philosophical concepts underlying descriptive cataloging.

University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign

To develop and evaluate online catalog interface enhancements that will provide expanded subject access to library collections through external databases.

Program Meetings, 1986/1987**Bibliographic Service Development Program Linked Systems Project**

Policy Committee

July 22, 1986 (Washington, D.C.)

December 9, 1986 (Washington, D.C.)

February 4, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

Technical Committee

September 4, 1986 (San Francisco)

December 11, 1986 (Washington, D.C.)

April 22, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

June 24, 1987 (San Francisco)

Impact of Nonserial Holdings Standard on USMARC Format for Holdings and Locations

November 6, 1986 (Washington, D.C.)

Network Advisory Committee

July 9–11, 1986 (Washington, D.C.)

December 10–12, 1986 (Washington, D.C.)

April 22–24, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

Librarianship and Librarians

Library directors and university administrators continue to voice concern about recruiting the necessary talent for the research library of the future. The education and role of librarians have been much discussed topics within and beyond the profession. Nearly all of the problems cited are symptoms of what must be described as a persistent shortage of distinctive professional leadership in all settings and at all levels.

CLR has supported several different programs—some for library schools, others for individuals—to address this concern. In 1986/87, the University of Madison-Wisconsin completed its research methods program for academic librarians, and the University of Chicago brought several experts in computing and information systems to the campus to conduct seminars and to broaden the curriculum of the Graduate Library School.

In the Internships for Recent Graduates program, the University of Georgia and three libraries in the Chicago area selected second classes of interns. In each case, staff members who had recently completed library school were chosen to participate in seminars, classes, and discussion groups designed to increase awareness of the complexity of university research library operations. New internship programs were initiated at the University of Missouri-Columbia and at Columbia University. A grant to Yale University provided summer internships for three Yale undergraduates to introduce them to research librarianship as a possible career.

Jeffrey Horrell, a CLR management intern, completed his nine-month program at Syracuse University with director David Stam. The CLR Board approved another cycle of Academic Library Management Internships for 1988/89.

In order to assess CLR's efforts in professional education and to explore new possibilities, a meeting was held at the Aspen Institute, Wye Plantation, November 9–11. Library school deans, library directors, and foundation officers considered fundamental questions concerning information studies, the information professions, and research library leadership. Following that meeting, a Committee on Information Studies was established (Committee members are listed in Appendix A). The Committee, made up of CLR Board members and distinguished educators, will consider ways to increase the

number of professional leaders. A report will be prepared during the winter of 1987-88.

Two cycles of cooperative research grants resulted in funding for seventeen research proposals. These cooperative research grants, listed separately beginning on page 26, have been valuable for stimulating collaboration between practicing librarians and teaching faculty.

Professional Education Projects, 1986/1987

Association of Research Libraries

To enable the Office of Management Studies to design and conduct a third Institute for Library Educators.

Columbia University

To plan a Library Fellows Program that will provide substantive orientation for librarians new to the profession and the research library environment.

Indiana University

To commission three papers for a forum on research librarianship for Indiana University librarians and School of Library and Information Science faculty.

Georgia State University

To conduct a study of occupational role identity and role image in four subspecialties of librarianship.

Louisiana State University

To implement a multidisciplinary curriculum for library systems analysts.

University of California, Los Angeles

To continue the Senior Fellows Program, which provides senior library administrators with opportunities for independent research and intensive, specialized study in management.

University of Chicago

For a multi-institutional internship program for recently hired library school graduates. Those involved are the University of Chicago Library and Graduate Library School, Northwestern University Libraries, and the University of Illinois at Chicago Library.

University of Chicago

To implement a special concentration in library automation and information systems and to stimulate awareness of the program within the university and library communities.

University of Georgia

To develop an internship program to introduce recently hired library school graduates to the full range of issues important to the university and to librarianship generally.

University of Michigan

To build a cooperative academic/internship program for library school students, involving the University Library and the Library School.

University of Missouri, Columbia

To establish a postgraduate internship program for librarians new to the profession.

University of Wisconsin, Madison

To implement a two-year academic program to improve problem-recognition and problem-solving capabilities of librarians through training in research methods.

Yale University

To recruit undergraduates at Yale University for the Yale Library Internship Program.

Faculty/Librarian Cooperative Research Projects 1982–1986 Grants Active in Fiscal 1987

Ruth Person, Catholic University, and George Charles Newman, State University of New York at Buffalo

To study the selection process for university library directors.

Katherine Chiang, Howard Curtis, Linda Stewart, and J. Robert Cooke, Cornell University

To test the use of microcomputer technology for supporting access to large bibliographic data files and to make a MEDLARS database subset available to users.

Michael L. Tomlan and Judith Holliday, Cornell University

To search for certain nineteenth-century American architectural periodicals held outside research libraries.

Sara Woolpy and Jerome H. Woolpy, Earlham College

To study the use of online abstracts as a source of information for undergraduate research.

Merrill W. Smith and Patrick A. Purcell, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

To examine the electronic delivery of visual images and text from the library to the academic community.

Andrew Torok and Jitka Hurych, Northern Illinois University

To study online searching of bibliographic and numeric databases.

Lloyd Davidson, Northwestern University, and Julie Hurd, University of Chicago

To analyze Chemical Abstracts Service online end user transaction logs and user behavior.

Marianne Cooper and Shoshana Kaufmann, Queens College of the City University of New York

To examine the relationships between library schools and academic libraries in the same institutions, and identify factors that encourage or hinder development of cooperative efforts.

Thomas T. Surprenant, Queens College, Barbara Moran, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, and Merrily Taylor, Brown University

To explore the role of the library in Brown University's efforts to incorporate electronic technologies in teaching, learning, and research.

Arthur Downing and Daniel O'Connor, Rutgers University

To study undergraduates' preferences for the number of bibliographic citations obtained through online searching.

Richard S. Halsey and Ruth Fraley, State University of New York, Albany

To conduct a market study of the information needs of scholars in the public affairs and policy department at Rockefeller College, SUNY-Albany.

Nancy B. Nuzzo and William E. McGrath, State University of New York, Buffalo

To validate statistically the Research Libraries Group Conspectus for music.

Neil Yerkey and Maryruth Glogowski, State University of New York, Buffalo

To determine how citations relevant to library and information science are scattered among machine-readable bibliographic databases.

Mary Biggs, University of Chicago, and Victor Biggs, Lake Forest College

To study collection development policies for academic library reference collections.

Betty Taylor, Elizabeth Mann, and Robert J. Munro, University of Florida

To study the impact of automation on the law school library budget, and the implications for library budgeting in general.

Beverly P. Lynch and Jo Ann Verdin, University of Illinois at Chicago

To replicate an investigation of the nature of the work of university libraries, and to assess the impact of technological change on organizational structure, task characteristics, communication patterns, unit output, and job satisfaction.

Carolyn O. Frost and Bonnie A. Dede, University of Michigan

To test subject heading compatibility between the Library of Congress Subject Headings and the University Library's catalog for automated authority control.

Helen Lloyd Snoke and Jean T. Loup, University of Michigan

For a comparison of the approval plan profiles of academic research libraries.

Rosie Albritton and Mary Ellen Sievert, University of Missouri, Columbia

To explore the effects of staff attitudes toward computer technology on their levels of participation in a library computer literacy program.

Mark Rorvig, Allison Beck, and David Gracy, University of Texas, Austin

To create a digitized, facsimile version of graphic images in the University's collections and measure users' reactions to the product.

James H. Sweetland and Wilfred Fong, University of Wisconsin, Milwaukee

To evaluate the effects of book reviews on library purchasing decisions.

Ralph A. Gustafson, Ronald J. Chepesiuk, and Gloria Kelley, Winthrop College

To evaluate the effectiveness of several chemicals against mold growth (mildew) in library collections.

1986/1987 Faculty/Librarian Cooperative Research Grants

Daniel Boyarski and Henry A. Pisciotta, Carnegie Mellon University

To produce a graphic database searching tutorial that will be used to teach individuals how to employ basic database searching techniques.

Joseph McDonald and Lynda Micikas, Holy Family College

To develop and test a method of syllabus analysis as a way for faculty to participate in collection development.

Richard Busch, Liang-tseng Fan, M. Dale Hawley, Delbert Mueller, and Robert Schwarzwald, Kansas State University

To develop a method of improving access to NTIS reports on microfiche, and evaluate the potential of this approach for improving library service.

Danny P. Wallace, Alma Dawson, and Bert Boyce, Louisiana State University

To develop a core library collection for library automation by creating a set of lists of monographs and serials relevant to education for library automation and proposing a procedure for maintaining current records.

Rich Hines and Candy Schwartz, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

To plan, develop, and implement an online gateway between library users and MIT library systems and services.

Celia Wall, John Griffin, and Roger Haney, Murray State University

To study the effects in small liberal arts colleges of the availability of online databases upon the continuation of subscriptions for the printed versions of the same databases.

Gilbert Krulee and Brian Nielsen, Northwestern University

To develop an intelligent support system for the reference librarian, using artificial intelligence techniques to respond to natural language queries.

Steven Atkinson and Geraldine Walker, State University of New York at Albany

To use measures of search recall to compare the coverage of different online databases and the effectiveness of natural language and controlled vocabulary for online retrieval for research in the humanities.

Howard Pikoff and James Pomerantz, State University of New York at Buffalo

To develop and evaluate a faculty notification system in which RLG acquisitions lists will be used in combination with limited document retrieval to improve access to new interdisciplinary holdings.

Susan Bonzi and Dorcas MacDonald, Syracuse University

To study the effect of online bibliographic retrieval services on the quality of service provided by an interlibrary loan department, as well as costs and cost-effectiveness of online ordering services.

David Stam and Michael Nilan, Syracuse University

To prepare for reorganization planning by assessing the library system from the perspectives of library users and library staff.

Gloriana St. Clair and Rose Mary Magrill, Texas A&M University

To study undergraduate use of a library's collection by identifying and analyzing patterns of use of library materials across class levels and disciplines.

Dorothy McGarry, University of California, Los Angeles, and Sheila Intner, Simmons College

To analyze the fullness and accuracy of member-contributed cataloging in OCLC and RLIN.

James Danowski, Robert Daugherty, and Stephen Wiberley, University of Illinois at Chicago

To evaluate user persistence in scanning online public access catalog postings by determining whether most online catalog users abandon a search after a certain number of postings.

Herbert Goldhor, David Self, and Priscilla Smiley, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

To determine the extent of in-house use of library materials in a scientific library.

Jin Moo Choi and Nancy Washington, University of South Carolina

To study the learning styles of university librarians and the implications for their professional development.

Mark Kinnucan, Henry Overduin, Victoria Ripley, and Elizabeth Howes, University of Western Ontario

To enhance a test collection of online public access catalog records with tables of contents, for the purpose of upgrading search and retrieval effectiveness.

Program Meetings, 1986/1987

Information Studies, the Information Professions, and Research Library Leadership

November 9–11, 1986 (Wye Plantation, Maryland)

Committee on Information Studies

April 29, 1987 (New York City)

Preservation

Preservation of print on paper has been a continuing concern of the Council since 1956. A review of CLR's annual reports provides a telling narrative of the growing understanding of the problem of paper deterioration. A typical entry can be found in the CLR *Annual Report* of 1969, which quotes a report on brittle books: "The volume of deteriorating materials requires that action be taken in the near future, if the nineteenth century is not to become known as the beginning of the bookless age."

The narrative of the Council's involvement continued in 1986/87 with a dramatic increase in preservation-related activities. The Commission on Preservation and Access—created in April 1986 on the recommendation of a precursor group—became a functioning reality, approving the hiring of a president and program officer as full-time staff and meeting five times during the year.

Funding for the Commission's work came in the form of grants and pledges from sixteen universities, two public libraries, a private foundation, and the Council. Financial viability was thus assured for an initial period of several years, during which the Commission will work to help create a coordinated national program to save significant numbers of deteriorating books in research libraries throughout the nation.

Activities undertaken by Commission and staff during the first year of operation reflect the complexity of the brittle books challenge. In March, members of the Commission, the Librarian of Congress, and others testified at a special Congressional hearing on brittle books. Throughout the year, articles appeared in national magazines, newspapers, and professional journals, describing the problem of deteriorating printed materials. A brochure outlining the work of the Commission and its companion organization, the National Advisory Council on Preservation, was published and distributed. The Advisory Council, comprising twenty organizations representing the academic, scholarly, archival, and library communities, held its first meeting in March and will be called upon increasingly in the coming year to promote widespread participation in national preservation goals.

A documentary film, "Slow Fires: On the Preservation of the Human Record," was produced by the American Film Foundation with funding from

the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the National Endowment for the Humanities, and CLR, and with the support of the Library of Congress. The film's first showing was at the Library of Congress at a joint meeting of the Commission and the Advisory Council. The film is available for sale or rental by the producer under a contractual arrangement with the Council.

The Council commissioned several projects addressing a range of technical and management issues related to the establishment of a coordinated national brittle books program, including a study of collection overlap, an analysis of the costs of preservation microfilming, and a comparison of formats for preserving the contents of brittle materials.

A series of meetings was held with library directors, preservation officers, and others to explore technical and managerial issues related to the operation of a national program, including questions of selection, bibliographic tracking, and preservation technology.

The Commission's work during the year reconfirmed the need expressed in a variety of ways over the previous thirty years—that of saving the content of at least a portion of the library materials at risk while there is still time, and, in the process, forming the core of a new national collection of preserved materials accessible to all.

However, while there is widespread agreement on the nature of the brittle book issue, much remains to be done to reach similar agreement on the means to accomplish the goal of preserving the contents of embrittled materials. During the coming year, the Commission and its staff will address a large number of the technical, financial, organizational, and attitudinal issues that must be resolved before large-scale preservation activity can begin.

Among the immediate issues is the format in which the contents of brittle books will be preserved. Given that most brittle books themselves do not warrant physical preservation, their contents must be recorded in a format that is proved to be long-lived. While many in the library community hope that optical and magnetic disk technologies will eventually offer archival longevity, at present the best means of achieving that longevity appears to be microfilm. And although microfilm is generally accepted as the best technology currently available for preserving text, in actual use it is frequently seen as a necessary evil. Thus, a careful study of format specifications and demonstrations of practical systems will be required before large-scale preservation microfilming can begin.

Other immediate issues include: agreement on the bibliographic procedures required to provide the base for an accessible and comprehensive record of preservation work; a method for selecting materials to be preserved; and an accurate assessment of costs involved in a large-scale program.

Finally, the Commission is aware that while the goal is to capture and make accessible the content of brittle books, the long-range solution to the problem must include the increasing use of acid-free paper and perhaps alternate technologies in all kinds of publishing. These and related activities will continue to be emphasized by the Commission as it pursues the immediate task of preservation and access.

Preservation Projects, 1986/1987

American Film Foundation

To produce a film on the preservation of library and archival materials.

American Film Foundation

To produce a half-hour version of the preservation film.

Robert M. Hayes

To obtain data relating to the costs of preservation and overlap of collections in several Association of Research Libraries member libraries.

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions

To help plan new core programs, including preservation and Universal Access to Publications, and to establish a management structure for those programs.

Library of Congress

To complete a series of training videotapes on library preservation and to distribute copies.

National Information Standards Organization

For development of an American National Standard for hard cover edition bindings.

Special Libraries Association

To underwrite a special issue of *Picturescope* on the subject of photo conservation and preservation.

Tantalus Inc.

To study preservation microfilming in four libraries, including assessment of cost determination, task analysis/job design, and quality control.

Program Meetings, 1986/1987

Commission on Preservation and Access

October 6, 1986 (Washington, D.C.)

January 26, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

March 1-2, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

March 20, 1987 (New York City)

June 4, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

Joint meeting with the National Advisory Council on Preservation

March 2, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

Planning for a National Brittle Books Program
April 30, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

Preservation Technology Forums
July 29, 1986 (Washington, D.C.)
December 10, 1986 (Bethesda, Maryland)
February 26, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

Appendix A

Program Committees and Project Participants

BIBLIOGRAPHIC SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM LINKED SYSTEMS PROJECT

LSP POLICY COMMITTEE

Henriette Avram

Library of Congress

David Bishop

University of Georgia

Rowland Brown

*OCLC Online Computer Library
Center*

Richard Dougherty

University of Michigan

Dorothy Gregor

University of California, San Diego

Mary Ellen Jacob

*OCLC Online Computer Library
Center*

Richard McCoy

*The Research Libraries Group, Inc.
(Resigned, December 1986)*

N. A. Stussy

Western Library Network

William P. Timlake

*The Research Libraries Group, Inc.
(Beginning February 1987)*

Nancy Zussy

*Western Library Network
(Resigned, July 1986)*

LSP TECHNICAL COMMITTEE

- | | |
|--|---|
| David Bishop (Chair)
<i>University of Georgia</i> | Roy Manicke
<i>Western Library Network</i>
<i>(Beginning March 1986)</i> |
| James Aagaard
<i>Northwestern University Library</i> | Michael Monahan
<i>Geac Computers International, Inc.</i>
<i>(Resigned, January 1987)</i> |
| Richard Adrion
<i>National Science Foundation</i>
<i>(Resigned, July 1986)</i> | David Pcolar
<i>Triangle Research Libraries Network</i>
<i>(Beginning June 1987)</i> |
| Edwin Buchinski
<i>National Library of Canada</i> | Jeanne Sawyer
<i>Triangle Research Libraries Network</i>
<i>(Resigned, June 1987)</i> |
| Wayne Davison
<i>The Research Libraries Group, Inc.</i> | Robert Schultheisz
<i>National Library of Medicine</i>
<i>(Beginning October 1986)</i> |
| Ray Denenberg
<i>Library of Congress</i> | Keith Thomas
<i>Geac Computers International, Inc.</i>
<i>(Beginning April 1987)</i> |
| Ahmed El-Hoshy
<i>National Library of Medicine</i>
<i>(Resigned, October 1986)</i> | |
| Larry Learn
<i>OCLC Online Computer Library</i>
<i>Center</i> | |

COMMITTEE ON INFORMATION STUDIES

- | | |
|--|---|
| William O. Baker
<i>Former Chairman of the Board,</i>
<i>Bell Telephone Laboratories</i> | Billy E. Frye
<i>Dean of the Graduate School & Vice</i>
<i>President for Research, Emory</i>
<i>University</i> |
| Patricia Battin
<i>Vice President & University</i>
<i>Librarian, Columbia University</i> | Neil Harris
<i>Professor of History, University of</i>
<i>Chicago</i> |
| Harvey Brooks
<i>Benjamin Peirce Professor of</i>
<i>Technology and Public Policy</i>
<i>Emeritus, Harvard University</i> | William N. Hubbard, Jr.
<i>Former President, Upjohn Company</i> |
| John H. D'Arms
<i>Dean of the Graduate School,</i>
<i>University of Michigan</i> | Neil Rudenstine
<i>Provost, Princeton University</i> |
| | William D. Schaefer
<i>Vice Chancellor, UCLA</i> |

COMMISSION ON PRESERVATION AND ACCESS

Millicent Abell <i>Yale University</i>	Kenneth Gros Louis <i>Indiana University</i>
Herbert Bailey <i>Princeton University Press (retired)</i>	Carole Huxley <i>New York State Education Department</i>
Billy Frye (Chair) <i>Emory University</i>	Sidney Verba <i>Harvard University</i>
James Govan <i>University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill</i>	William Welsh <i>Library of Congress</i>
Vartan Gregorian <i>New York Public Library</i>	

The Commission on Preservation and Access was formed in the spring of 1986 to continue the work of the CLR Committee on Preservation and Access. While the Commission is an independent body, CLR is providing financial and administrative support during the Commission's formative period. Funding for the first three years of the Commission's work is being provided by CLR, the H. W. Wilson Foundation, and the following:

Columbia University
Harvard University
Indiana University
Princeton University
Stanford University
University of California, Berkeley
University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign
University of Michigan
Yale University

Participants in the New York State Preservation Program

Appendix B

Publications and Reports Resulting From CLR Programs, 1986–1987

Part I. Publications of the Council and CLR Staff

American Film Foundation. "Slow Fires: On the Preservation of the Human Record" (one-hour film). Washington, D.C.: Council on Library Resources, May 1987.

"The Commission on Preservation and Access" (brochure). April 1987.

Cummings, Martin M. "Information to Manage: The Economics of Research Libraries." In *Research Libraries: Measurements, Management, Marketing*, 9–11. Washington, D.C.: Association of Research Libraries, 1986.

Kantor, Paul B. *Costs of Preservation Microfilming at Research Libraries: A Study of Four Institutions*. Washington, D.C.: Council on Library Resources, November 1986.

Lowry, Anita, and Junko Stuveras, comps. *Scholarship in the Electronic Age: A Selected Bibliography on Research and Communication in the Humanities and Social Sciences*. Washington, D.C.: Council on Library Resources, February 1987.

Mandel, Carol A. *Classification Schedules as Subject Enhancement in Online Catalogs: A Review of a Conference Sponsored by Forest Press, the OCLC Online Computer Library Center, and the Council on Library Resources*. Washington, D.C.: Council on Library Resources, October 1986.

Thompson, Mary Agnes. "Council on Library Resources, Inc." In *The Bowker Annual of Library and Book Trade Information*, 32d ed., 238–43. New York: Bowker, 1987.

Part II. Publications by Grantees and Contractors

Avram, Henriette D., and Beacher Wiggins. "The Role of the Linked Systems Project in Cooperation and Resource Sharing Among Libraries." *Libraries & Computing Centers: Issues of Mutual Concern*, no. 2 (May 1987): 1–4.

Chan, Lois Mai. "Library of Congress Classification as an Online Retrieval Tool: Potentials and Limitations." *Information Technology and Libraries* 5 (September 1986): 181–92.

- Denenberg, Ray. "NISO Draft Standard Z39.50: Information Retrieval Protocol." *Library Hi Tech News*, no. 39 (June 1987): 1, 7-8.
- . "Standard Network Interconnection." *Information Technology and Libraries* 5 (December 1986): 314-23.
- Frost, Carolyn O. "Faculty Use of Subject Searching in Card and Online Catalogs." *Journal of Academic Librarianship* 13 (May 1987): 86-92.
- . "Subject Searching in an Online Catalog." *Information Technology and Libraries* 6 (March 1987): 60-63.
- Futas, Elizabeth, and David L. Vidor. "How Business Professionals Use Libraries: A Survey of Graduate Students and Graduates." *Library Journal* 111 (November 1, 1986): 35-39.
- . "What Constitutes a 'Good' Collection?" *Library Journal* 112 (April 15, 1987): 45-47.
- Gothberg, Helen M. "Time Management and the Woman Library Manager." *Library Journal* 112 (May 1, 1987): 37-40.
- Hayes, Robert M. "Strategic Planning for Information Resources in the Research University." *RQ* 25 (Summer 1986): 427-31.
- Hyatt, James A., and Aurora A. Santiago. *University Libraries in Transition*. Washington, D.C.: National Association of College and University Business Officers, 1987.
- International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions. "IFLA and the Third World: the IFLA Core Programme on the Advancement of Librarianship in the Third World (ALP)." The Hague: IFLA, 1986.
- Jamieson, Alexis J., Elizabeth Dolan, and Luc Declerck. "Keyword Searching vs. Authority Control in an Online Catalog." *Journal of Academic Librarianship* 12 (November 1986): 277-83.
- Johnson, Jean S. "Collection Management for Off-Campus Library Services." *Library Acquisitions* 11 (1987): 75-84.
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- [Linked Systems Project Policy Committee.] "Agreement is Reached on LSP Priorities and Issues." *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 45 (December 15, 1986): 403.
- Lipetz, Ben-Ami, and Peter J. Paulson. "A Study of the Impact of Introducing an Online Subject Catalog at the New York State Library." *Library Trends* 35 (Spring 1987): 597-617.
- Lynch, Beverly P., and Jo Ann Verdin. "Job Satisfaction in Libraries: A Replication." *The Library Quarterly* 57 (April 1987): 190-202.
- McCallum, Sally H. "The Linked Systems Project: Implications for Library Automation & Networking." In *Advances in Library Automation Networking*, edited by Joseph A. Hewitt. Greenwich, Conn.: JAI Press, 1987.
- McCoy, Richard W. "The Linked Systems Project." *Library Journal* 111 (October 1, 1986): 33-46.
- Marchionini, Gary, and Danuta A. Nitecki. "Managing Change: Supporting Users of Automated Sys-

- tems." *College & Research Libraries* 48 (March 1987): 104-9.
- Markey, Karen. "Class Number Searching in an Experimental Online Catalog." *International Classification* 13 (1986): 142-50.
- Martin, J. Sperling. "Electronic Document Interchange and the AAP Electronic Manuscript Project." *Library Hi Tech* 4, no. 3 (Fall 1986): 31-42.
- Matthews, Joseph R. "Suggested Guidelines for Screen Layouts and Design of Online Catalogs." *Library Trends* 35 (Spring 1987): 555-70.
- Molyneux, Robert E. "Growth at ARL Libraries, 1962/63 to 1983/84." *Journal of Academic Librarianship* 12 (September 1986): 212-16.
- . "Staffing Patterns and Library Growth at ARL Libraries, 1962/63 to 1983/84." *Journal of Academic Librarianship* 12 (November 1986): 292-97.
- Moran, Barbara B., Thomas T. Surprenant, and Merrily E. Taylor. "The Electronic Campus: The Impact of the Scholar's Workstation Project on the Libraries at Brown." *College & Research Libraries* 48 (January 1987): 5-16.
- Nelson, Anna Kasten. "The 1985 Report of the Committee on the Records of Government: An Assessment." *Government Information Quarterly* 4 (1987): 143-50.
- Nielsen, Brian, and Betsy Baker. "Educating the Online Catalog User: A Model Evaluation Study." *Library Trends* 35 (Spring 1987): 571-85.
- Powell, Ronald R., and Nancy Becker Johnson. "Education for Research Librarianship: A Preliminary Assessment of the Michigan Program." *Journal of Education for Library & Information Science* 27 (Winter 1987): 169-84.
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- Stone, Elizabeth W. "Continuing Education for the Library and Information Professions: An International Perspective, 1985." *IFLA Journal* 12 (1986): 203-17.
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Part III. Project Reports Received

Many project reports are published in the professional literature. Authors retain ownership of the reports and are asked to submit copies to the ERIC database. ERIC document numbers that have been reported to CLR are listed at the end of the citation. Inquiries about reports without an ERIC number should be addressed to the author.

- Albritton, Rosie L., and MaryEllen Sievert. "Investigating the Effects of Human Factors on the Outcome of a Library Computer Literacy Program." Columbia: University of Missouri, March 1987.
- Biggs, Mary, and Victor Biggs. "Report to the Council on Library Resources [on a Study of Collection Development Policies in U.S. Academic Library Reference Departments]." January 1987. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Ferguson, Anthony W., Joan Grant, and Joel Rutstein. "The Conceptus: A Primer for Educators." Stanford, April 1987.
- Lynch, Beverly P., and Jo Ann Verdin. "Relationship of Technology and Characteristics of Library Functional Units." Chicago, December 1986. ED 278 427. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- "OCLC's Implementation of the Linked System Protocols for Name Authority Applications." Dublin, Ohio: OCLC, April 1987.
- Person, Ruth J., and George Charles Newman. "Selection of the University Librarian." June 1987. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Smith, Merrill W., Patrick A. Purcell, and Christopher P. Thorman. "Visual Image Transmission: An Examination of Electronic Delivery of Visual Images and Text from the Library to the Academic Community." September 1986. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
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- Taylor, Betty W., Elizabeth B. Mann, and Robert J. Munro. "The Twenty-first Century: Technology's Impact on Academic and Research and Law Libraries Including Projections for Fiscal Planning." University of Florida, September 1986. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Woodsworth, Anne. "The Roles and Responsibilities of the Senior Information Manager at Selected American Universities." Pittsburgh, October 1986. ED 279 343.
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Appendix C

Program Guidelines and Grant Application Procedures

The Council on Library Resources supports work by individuals and organizations on matters pertinent to library service and information systems, with the primary objective of improving the quality and performance of academic and research libraries. Individuals with specific interests and expertise are encouraged to take the initiative and propose for consideration projects within the broad areas of the Council's program, as described in this report.

In addition, CLR sponsors special programs, such as that offering support for cooperative research projects involving librarians and teaching faculty. Such programs are described in brochures available from CLR.

Application Procedures

Initial inquiries should state the purpose of the proposed work, identify the methods to be used, establish the credentials of the responsible individuals, and provide a careful estimate of total costs and funding requirements. CLR will respond promptly with an indication of interest. If subsequent exploration seems justified, preparation of a complete proposal will be suggested. Full documentation should include:

1. A fifty-word description of the proposed project.
2. A full explanation of the work to be done, including objectives, duration, and methods to be employed. Background information (including a literature review) and the methods proposed for project evaluation should also be included.
3. A detailed project budget in which costs are linked to the tasks to be performed. CLR does not fund indirect costs, normal operating costs, or equipment purchases.
4. Curricula vitae of the principal investigators.

All proposals are carefully reviewed by CLR staff and external advisors, who consider such matters as relevance to current CLR interests and activities;

relationship to other, similar work; projected costs in the context of the work required; and importance of anticipated results. The Council also looks for institutional support of a proposed project, as demonstrated by a willingness to share in the costs of the enterprise. With the exception of the special programs noted above, there are no deadlines for grant proposals.

All inquiries should be addressed to Council on Library Resources, 1785 Massachusetts Avenue, N.W., Washington, D.C. 20036.

ACTIVE PROJECTS

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Acknowledgement

The following pages record grants and contracts active during fiscal year 1987 and, through audited financial reports, provide an overall picture of CLR income and expenditures.

Financial support for CLR activities comes from many sources. On behalf of the academic and research library community, we express gratitude to:

The Carnegie Corporation of New York
The Exxon Education Foundation
The Ford Foundation
The J. Paul Getty Trust
The German Marshall Fund of the United States
The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation
The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation
The National Endowment for the Humanities
The Pew Charitable Trusts
The Alfred P. Sloan Foundation
The H. W. Wilson Foundation

We also acknowledge the support for the Commission on Preservation and Access from the universities listed on page 35 of this report.

Grants and Contracts Active in Fiscal 1987 (unaudited)

	FY 1987			
	Unpaid 6/30/86	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/87
American Antiquarian Society				
Worcester, Mass.				
Completion of the North American Imprints Program	\$ -0-	\$ 30,000	\$ 15,000	\$ 15,000
American Film Foundation				
Santa Monica, Calif.				
Production of a documentary film on the preservation of library materials	160,000	-0-	160,000	-0-
Thirty-minute version of the preservation film	16,500	-0-	12,500	4,000
American Geographical Society				
New York, N.Y.				
Planning for a new <i>Columbia Gazetteer of the World</i>	7,500	-0-	7,500	-0-
American Historical Association				
Washington, D.C.				
Planning meeting for a new <i>Guide to Historical Literature</i>	-0-	6,780	-0-	6,780
Association of Research Libraries				
Washington, D.C.				
Institute for library educators				
Third—1988	-0-	45,000	20,000	25,000
Second—1986	5,857	-0-	-0-	5,857
Trudi Bellardo				
Washington, D.C.				
History of online information retrieval systems	-0-	2,000	1,000	1,000

	<u>FY 1987</u>			
	Unpaid 6/30/86	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/87
Carleton College				
Northfield, Minn.				
Index to microform collections, Volume 2	300	-0-	300	-0-
Carnegie Mellon University				
Pittsburgh, Pa.				
Establish a study group on the structure of electronic text	-0-	15,000	12,000	3,000
Production of a pilot version of a database searching tutorial	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Columbia University				
New York, N.Y.				
Bibliography on the impact of the information revolution on scholarship in the humanities and social sciences	-0-	7,630	7,630	-0-
Library fellows program	44,450	-0-	20,000	24,450
Measuring the public services impact of an online catalog	11,200	-0-	-0-	11,200
Enoch Pratt Free Library				
Baltimore, Md.				
Centennial symposium	-0-	5,000	4,000	1,000
European Foundation for Library Cooperation				
The Hague, Netherlands				
Development funds	-0-	18,000	17,000	1,000
Georgia State University				
Atlanta, Ga.				
Study of occupational role identity and image of specialties in librarianship	-0-	4,649	4,000	649
Robert M. Hayes				
Los Angeles, Calif.				
Study of preservation costs and benefits	30,100	-0-	10,000	20,100

	<u>FY 1987</u>			
	Unpaid 6/30/86	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/87
Holy Family College				
Philadelphia, Pa.				
Syllabi analysis for faculty participation in collection development	-0-	1,466	-0-	1,466
Indiana University				
Bloomington, Ind.				
Papers for a forum series on research librarianship	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions				
The Hague, Netherlands				
Planning IFLA core programs	44,000	-0-	44,000	-0-
Report on copyright and materials for the handicapped	1,000	(1,000)	-0-	-0-
Kansas State University				
Manhattan, Kans.				
Development of a method of improving access to NTIS reports on microfiche	-0-	2,807	-0-	2,807
Library of Congress				
Washington, D.C.				
Bibliographic analysis— Linked Systems Project	3,120	-0-	1,500	1,620
Completion of a series of training videotapes on library preservation	-0-	15,110	14,000	1,110
International conference on preservation of library materials	2,250	-0-	-0-	2,250
Symposium on incunabula in American libraries	-0-	5,000	5,000	-0-

	<u>FY 1987</u>			
	Unpaid 6/30/86	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/87
Louisiana State University				
Baton Rouge, La.				
Development of a core collection for library automation	-0-	2,861	2,861	-0-
Development of a curriculum for library systems analysts	34,000	-0-	20,000	14,000
Massachusetts Institute of Technology				
Cambridge, Mass.				
Development and implementation of an online gateway between library users and MIT library services	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000
Murray State University				
Murray, Ky.				
Study of the effect of the availability of online databases on subscriptions for printed versions of the same databases	-0-	1,535	1,535	-0-
National Association of College and University Business Officers				
Washington, D.C.				
Study of strategic planning in university libraries	1,000	-0-	1,000	-0-
National Information Standards Organization				
Gaithersburg, Md.				
Development of an American national standard for hardcover edition bindings	25,000	-0-	1,262	23,738
Northwestern University				
Evanston, Ill.				
Development of a reference process model	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Implementation of the standard network interconnection in a local library system	-0-	25,000	15,000	10,000

	FY 1987			
	Unpaid 6/30/86	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/87
OCLC Online Computer Library Center Dublin, Ohio				
Increase accessibility of Library of Congress subject headings in online bibliographic systems	-0-	93,700	-0-	93,700
Participation in the Linked Systems Project	24,000	-0-	24,000	-0-
Pennsylvania State University University Park, Pa.				
Development of library consortial relationships	-0-	3,000	2,500	500
Ruth Person Washington, D.C.				
Study of the selection process for university librarians	1,000	(653)	347	-0-
Queens College Flushing, N.Y.				
Examining relationships between library schools and their institutions' libraries	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-
The Research Libraries Group, Inc. Stanford, Calif.				
Analysis of the RLG Conspectus as a collection management tool	10,000	-0-	4,500	5,500
Bibliographic analysis— Linked Systems Project	11,470	-0-	5,000	6,470
Creation of a national database of public records information	15,532	-0-	15,000	532
Joint project for authorities implementation	89,245	-0-	-0-	89,245
Travel support for RLG archives committee	5,000	-0-	1,008	3,992

	FY 1987			
	Unpaid 6/30/86	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/87
Special Libraries Association				
Washington, D.C.				
<i>Picturescope</i> issue on photo conservation and preservation	-0-	1,500	1,500	-0-
Stanford University				
Stanford, Calif.				
Investigation of end-user searching of bibliographic databases	4,300	-0-	-0-	4,300
State University of New York				
Albany, N.Y.				
Study of information needs of public affairs scholars	2,996	-0-	2,996	-0-
Study of online database research in the humanities	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000
State University of New York				
Buffalo, N.Y.				
Use of RLG acquisitions lists to improve access to new interdisciplinary holdings	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000
Study of statistical reliability of indicators in the RLG Conspectus for music	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-
Abigail Dahl-Hansen Studdiford				
Bridgewater, N.J.				
Study of public issues relating to research libraries	-0-	8,000	-0-	8,000
Syracuse University				
Syracuse, N.Y.				
Impact of computerized bibliographic retrieval services on the quality of an interlibrary loan department	-0-	2,975	2,975	-0-
Textual analysis of information needs derived from abstracts of documents	-0-	24,913	13,000	11,913

	<u>FY 1987</u>			
	Unpaid 6/30/86	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/87
User study in reorganization planning for university and research libraries	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Tantalus Inc.				
Cleveland, Ohio				
Study of preservation microfilming	4,670	(126)	4,544	-0-
Texas A & M University				
College Station, Tex.				
Analysis of undergraduate use of a library's collection	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
University of California				
Los Angeles, Calif.				
Analysis of member-contributed cataloging in OCLC and RLIN	-0-	2,170	2,170	-0-
Conference on conceptual foundations of cataloging	9,670	-0-	6,000	3,670
Research program: long-range strategic planning for libraries and information resources in research universities	350,000	-0-	-0-	350,000
Senior fellows program				
1983-85	56,392	(10,250)	46,142	-0-
1987	45,000	-0-	-0-	45,000
University of Chicago				
Chicago, Ill.				
Implementation of a concentration in library automation and information systems	39,500	-0-	-0-	39,500
Multi-institutional professional development program for recent library school graduates	36,960	-0-	24,739	12,221

	FY 1987			
	Unpaid 6/30/86	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/87
University of Georgia				
Athens, Ga.				
Internships for recent library school graduates	70,158	-0-	7,060	63,098
University of Illinois				
Chicago, Ill.				
Study of library users' persistence in scanning OPAC postings	-0-	1,200	-0-	1,200
Study of strategic planning issues for the research university	-0-	69,200	-0-	69,200
University of Illinois				
Urbana, Ill.				
Collection development and overlap in the LCS network in Illinois	3,320	(3,320)	-0-	-0-
Developing and evaluating online catalog interface enhancements	8,000	-0-	-0-	8,000
Study of in-house use of materials in the University of Illinois Veterinary Medicine Library	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
University of Kentucky				
Lexington, Ky.				
Bibliographic guide to indexing languages used in online databases	2,580	-0-	-0-	2,580
Second edition of <i>Library of Congress Subject Headings: Principles and Application</i>	360	(360)	-0-	-0-
University of Michigan				
Ann Arbor, Mich.				
Basic professional education for research librarianship	30,480	(30,480)	-0-	-0-

	FY 1987			
	Unpaid 6/30/86	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/87
Increase accessibility of Library of Congress subject headings in online bibliographic systems	-0-	47,925	-0-	47,925
Study of the relationship between bibliographic access to stored materials and faculty attitudes	16,863	(935)	15,928	-0-
University Library Associates Program	35,000	-0-	35,000	-0-
University of Minnesota				
St. Paul, Minn.				
Plan and design of a model academic integrated information center	-0-	117,000	-0-	117,000
University of Missouri				
Columbia, Mo.				
Internships for recent library school graduates	55,205	-0-	-0-	55,205
University of North Carolina				
Chapel Hill, N.C.				
Development of protocols for exchange of bibliographic records	29,670	(54,670)	(25,000)	-0-
University of Pittsburgh				
Pittsburgh, Pa.				
Study of roles of information managers in American universities	1,990	(599)	1,391	-0-
University of South Carolina				
Columbia, S.C.				
Study of learning styles of university librarians	-0-	2,960	-0-	2,960

	<u>FY 1987</u>			
	Unpaid 6/30/86	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/87
University of Western Ontario				
London, Canada				
Analysis of search effectiveness using tables of contents in OPACs	-0-	2,892	2,892	-0-
University of Wisconsin				
Madison, Wis.				
Development of a supplementary education program for academic and research librarians	20,612	-0-	15,935	4,677
University of Wisconsin				
Milwaukee, Wis.				
Study of the effects of published reviews on library purchasing decisions	2,965	-0-	2,965	-0-
Virginia Foundation for the				
Humanities and Public Policy				
Charlottesville, Va.				
Literature series for librarians	-0-	1,720	1,720	-0-
Western Library Network				
Olympia, Wash.				
Bibliographic analysis— Linked Systems Project	6,887	(6,887)	-0-	-0-
Joint project for authorities implementation	23,801	(23,801)	-0-	-0-
Winthrop College				
Rock Hill, S.C.				
Testing chemicals for mildew control in library materials	2,920	-0-	2,920	-0-
Yale University				
New Haven, Conn.				
Library internship program for Yale undergraduates	-0-	12,000	5,000	7,000

	<u>FY 1987</u>			
	Unpaid	Grants and Contracts	Payments	Unpaid
	6/30/86	(Adjustments)	(Refunds)	6/30/87
Other refunds and adjustments from prior years' grants and contracts	-0-	(7,503)	(7,503)	-0-
Totals	\$1,409,823	\$602,993 (140,584)	\$665,320 (32,503)	\$1,239,415

Opinion of Independent Accountants

August 14, 1987

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying balance sheets and the related statements of revenues, expenses and changes in fund balances, of functional expenses and of changes in cash and short-term investments present fairly the financial position of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1987 and 1986, the results of its operations for the year ended June 30, 1987 and the changes in its cash and short-term investments for the two years then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles consistently applied. Our examinations of these statements were made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

Price Waterhouse
Washington, D.C.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Balance Sheets

	June 30	
	<u>1987</u>	<u>1986</u>
ASSETS		
Cash and short-term investments, including restricted amounts of \$1,494,143 and \$1,705,365, respectively	\$4,357,102	\$4,362,363
Grants receivable (Notes 2 and 5)		
Unrestricted	1,800,000	
Restricted	2,383,164	2,954,164
Prepaid expenses and deposits	<u>12,475</u>	<u>6,848</u>
Total assets	<u><u>\$8,552,741</u></u>	<u><u>\$7,323,375</u></u>
LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE		
Deferred income (Note 2)		
Unrestricted	\$2,100,000	\$ 250,000
Restricted	2,700,613	3,378,609
Grants and contracts payable (Note 2)		
Unrestricted	62,721	128,903
Restricted	1,176,694	1,280,920
Accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	<u>60,586</u>	<u>40,852</u>
Total liabilities	<u>6,100,614</u>	<u>5,079,284</u>
Fund balance		
Appropriated	1,360,287	1,441,831
Unappropriated	<u>1,091,840</u>	<u>802,260</u>
Total fund balance	<u>2,452,127</u>	<u>2,244,091</u>
Total liabilities and fund balance	<u><u>\$8,552,741</u></u>	<u><u>\$7,323,375</u></u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balances

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1987

(With Comparative Totals for 1986)

	Unrestricted	Restricted	Total 1987	Total 1986*
Revenues (Note 2)				
Grants and contracts	\$ 550,000	\$753,136	\$1,303,136	\$2,320,890
Contributions		58,861	58,861	
Investment income	253,430		253,430	283,240
Total revenues	<u>803,430</u>	<u>811,997</u>	<u>1,615,427</u>	<u>2,604,130</u>
Expenses (Notes 2, 3 and 4)				
Program				
Research	10,443	438,739	449,182	627,120
Access	23,833	142,486	166,319	760,295
Bibliography	119,152	77,751	196,903	269,233
Librarianship	107,900	83,039	190,939	325,097
Preservation commission	110,753	69,982	180,735	3,250
Management				20,471
Total program	372,081	811,997	1,184,078	2,005,466
Administration	223,313		223,313	214,393
Total expenses	<u>595,394</u>	<u>811,997</u>	<u>1,407,391</u>	<u>2,219,859</u>
Excess of revenues over expenses	208,036		208,036	384,271
Fund balance, begin- ning of year	<u>2,244,091</u>		<u>2,244,091</u>	<u>1,859,820</u>
Fund balance, end of year	<u>\$2,452,127</u>		<u>\$2,452,127</u>	<u>\$2,244,091</u>

* Reclassified for comparability

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Statements of Changes in Cash and Short-term Investments

	Year ended June 30	
	<u>1987</u>	<u>1986</u>
Sources of cash and short-term investments		
Excess of revenues over expenses	\$ 208,036	\$ 384,271
Increase in grants and contracts payable		544,991
Increase in deferred income	1,172,004	
Decrease in grants receivable		2,454,836
Increase in accounts payable and accrued benefits	19,734	
	<u>1,399,774</u>	<u>3,384,098</u>
Uses of cash and short-term investments		
Increase in grants receivable	1,229,000	
Decrease in deferred income		2,496,890
Decrease in grants and contracts payable	170,408	
Other	5,627	4,604
	<u>1,405,035</u>	<u>2,501,494</u>
(Decrease) increase in cash and short-term investments for the year	(5,261)	882,604
Cash and short-term investments, beginning of year	<u>4,362,363</u>	<u>3,479,759</u>
Cash and short-term investments, end of year	<u>\$4,357,102</u>	<u>\$4,362,363</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

STATEMENT OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1987

(With Comparative Totals for 1986)

	Research	Access	Bibliography	Librarianship	Preservation Commission	Total Program	Administration	Year ended June 30	
								1987	1986*
Unrestricted									
Grants and contracts	\$ 10,000	\$ 26,290	\$ 4,356			\$ 40,646		\$ 40,646	\$ 109,420
Refunds and overappropriations		(2,470)	(3,320)	\$ (3,350)		(9,140)		(9,140)	(19,892)
Staff and travel			39,741	26,728	\$ 31,945	98,414	\$ 115,272	213,686	126,138
Advisory committees and consultants			22,065	32,320	2,547	56,932		56,932	10,792
Board expenses							22,548	22,548	18,322
Office expenses	443	13	32	135	1,224	1,847	10,456	12,303	29,742
Support services			56,278	52,067	75,037	183,382	75,037	258,419	74,447
	<u>10,443</u>	<u>23,833</u>	<u>119,152</u>	<u>107,900</u>	<u>110,753</u>	<u>372,081</u>	<u>223,313</u>	<u>595,394</u>	<u>348,969</u>
Restricted									
Grants and contracts	252,743	84,486	163,469	61,649		562,347		562,347	1,184,568
Refunds and overappropriations		(2,000)	(85,718)	(43,725)		(131,443)		(131,443)	(6,234)
Staff and travel	91,671	31,834		21,617	42,964	188,086		188,086	265,243
Advisory committees and consultants	16,786	8,066		19,123	23,446	67,421		67,421	157,156
Office expenses	2,502	1,341		1,405	3,572	8,820		8,820	12,229
Support services	75,037	18,759		22,970		116,766		116,766	257,928
	<u>438,739</u>	<u>142,486</u>	<u>77,751</u>	<u>83,039</u>	<u>69,982</u>	<u>811,997</u>		<u>811,997</u>	<u>1,870,890</u>
Total expenses	<u>\$449,182</u>	<u>\$166,319</u>	<u>\$196,903</u>	<u>\$190,939</u>	<u>\$180,735</u>	<u>\$1,184,078</u>	<u>\$223,313</u>	<u>\$1,407,391</u>	<u>\$2,219,859</u>

* Reclassified for comparability

Notes to Financial Statements

JUNE 30, 1987 AND 1986

Note 1—Organization

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research. The Council's operations are financed through unrestricted general support grants and through several restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work through directly administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

The Council, an exempt operating foundation, is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3).

Note 2—Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

The Council's financial statements have been prepared on the accrual basis of accounting. The significant accounting policies followed in the preparation of the financial statements are described below.

Grants

Grants are recorded as receivables and deferred revenue when the Council is notified that it has been awarded the funds. Unrestricted grant revenue is recognized in accordance with the budgeted annual payments specified by the grantors. Restricted grant revenue is recognized when the related expenses are incurred.

Grant and contract expenses are recorded when the recipients are notified that they are to receive the funds. Current period expenses are reduced for grant refunds and overappropriations.

Contributions

During fiscal year 1987 various universities made restricted contributions to support the Commission on Preservation and Access. Voluntary contributions to fund this program are recorded as deferred revenue when received. Contribution revenue is recognized when the related expenses are incurred.

Investments and investment income

Short-term investments, which primarily consist of treasury bills and interests in a money market fund, are recorded at cost which approximates market. Investment income is not restricted by the related grants and accordingly is recognized as unrestricted revenue.

Functional allocation of expenses

Costs of providing the various programs of the Council have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Certain indirect costs identified as support services costs have been allocated to programs and administra-

tion on a systematic basis. These costs primarily include salary, benefits, rent and other expenses.

Furniture and equipment

The costs of office furniture and equipment are consistently charged to expense when incurred. The Council does not consider such expenditures to be sufficiently material to warrant capitalization and depreciation.

Note 3—Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's defined contribution retirement annuity program administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the plan provide for full and immediate vesting of both the Council's and employees' contributions. The Council's contribution was \$59,000 and \$55,000 for fiscal years 1987 and 1986, respectively.

Note 4—Commitments

The Council entered into a lease agreement for office space expiring in 1990. The minimum future rentals will be approximately \$140,000 for each of the next three years. As part of this lease agreement, the Council will continue to be assessed an annual charge based on a proportionate share of the increase in operating costs of the building.

For the years ended June 30, 1987 and 1986, rent expense totalled \$124,000 and \$116,000, respectively, of which \$17,000 and \$8,000, respectively, represents the Council's share of the increase in operating costs.

The Council subleases a portion of its leased office space. Rental income from this sublease amounted to approximately \$32,000 and \$30,000 in fiscal years 1987 and 1986, respectively, and was used to offset office rent expense.

Note 5—Grant Transfer

On July 1, 1986 the Council was notified by a grantor foundation that it intended to redesignate a grant, presently awarded to the Council, when and if the present subrecipient received its Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3) status ruling. On July 20, 1987, the subrecipient received approval of its tax exempt status and the Council reduced its grants receivable and deferred revenue related to the restricted grant by \$496,000 at June 30, 1987.

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